

Original Article

Influence of digital video commercials (DVC) on buying behavior of youngsters

Nimra Waris¹, Dr. Muhammad Bilal Nawaz², Dr. Muhammad Bilal Bhatti³

¹ MS Mass Communication, Department of Mass Communication Lahore College for Women University, Lahore

²Assistant Professor, Department of Mass Communication Lahore College for Women University, Lahore

³Lecturer, Department of Mass Communication, Mirpur University of Science & Technology (MUST), Mirpur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan

Abstract

In this research, the point of focus was the youngsters and the analyzation of the effect of emerging trends of advertisement on them. With the help of survey, many different questions were asked from them to can to the conclusion that how effective these advertisements are. This paper consisted of different sections. In section one, there is introduction to the topic and its related background. In section two, there is literature review, which shows what studies were done before that are similar to this and what results were achieved. Then following these, there is methodology, finding and results, and discussion and conclusion. when the help of these sections, the paper was able to achieve the results and the conclusion successfully.

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How to Cite:

Waris, N., Nawaz, M.B., & Bhatti, M.B (2024). Influence of digital video commercials (DVC) on buying behavior of youngsters. *Journal of Social Horizons*, 1(2), 136-148.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17423116>

Keywords: Emerging Trends, Advertising, Digital Video Commercials (DVC), Buying Behavior of Youngsters

Introduction

Advertising has been a critical part of marketing since the dawn of commerce and free enterprise. The written word opened up a new contact line between the manufacturer and the customer. Publications, including newspapers, magazines, and catalogues, continue to publish print ads. The arrival of the radio sparked the advertising revolution. Television commercials eventually exceeded print commercials in popularity and significance. The use of television, radio and print ads to promote a company's products is still essential. Advertising is now more accessible than ever because of the advent of the Internet and mobile devices. It is possible that online advertising, which uses electronic or online media to transmit marketing messages and attract new customers while retaining existing ones, may lead to this outcome (Aaker, 2019).

Facebook

It is a social networking service launched in 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg and his Harvard University colleague. Facebook is one platform that facilitates worldwide engagement and the exchange of ideas and experiences among its members. Facebook is a social media site consisting of a "Web-based platform that facilitates a deeper social connection, a stronger community, and the realization of cooperative projects" (Brown, 2009).

* Corresponding Author: Dr. Muhammad Bilal Nawaz | Assistant Professor, Department of Mass Communication Lahore College for Women University, Lahore

✉ bilal.nawaz@lcwu.edu.pk

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Instagram

Kevin Systrom, a 27-year-old Stanford University alumnus, introduced the picture and video-sharing social media programme Instagram in 2010. On its first day of operation, October 6, 2010, the number of active users hit a staggering 250,000.

Objective

The objectives of this research are as follows:

- To research how fashion firms use Digital Video Commercials for social media advertising.
- To investigate the effect of DVC on young purchasing behaviour

Rational

This research aims to investigate the strategies of social media advertising and its consequences on young people's social structure and attitudes. In addition, the number of Pakistani fashion companies is rising, and the fashion business is expanding daily. Social media is now the largest advertising channel for the rising fashion sector. It would be fascinating to discover advertising rules in the increasing digitalization, social media, and fashion industries (Piah, 2018).

Statement of problem

In recent years, social media has had a great impact on the daily life of youngsters. Social media Instagram and Facebook occupy a large portion of youngster's life. Social media has achieved a central role in the lives of youth. Due to use of social media youngsters observed the advertising trends through video commercials and changed their buying behavior. Thus, it is important to understand the negative and positive effect of online buying behavior of youth.

This study had asserted to check out the online buying behavior of young people through social media advertising.

Literature Review

The audience is generated and targeted for advertising. Not only is it a marketplace for buying and selling, but it also informs us about global trends. Advertising is responsible for communicating commercial messages to the target audience. Advertising is a method of communication that offers the audience helpful and pertinent information to act immediately or utilize at the moment of purchase (Ankita Shrivastava, 2014). In the age of digitization, all of the world's leading companies have achieved a phenomenal following on social media. They use social media to safeguard their unique image in the eyes of their consumers. The Italian brand is increasing client loyalty by responding to user feedback and regularly publishing about items on social media. Because of the widespread use of mobile phones for communication, consumers' perceptions of advertising have shifted significantly. Customers may be more receptive to mobile promotions if they can get them at the right time and place. Teens have widely used mobile services like SMS and IM for several years. Teens use their mobile phones to keep in touch and have fun with their friends at all times and places (even at the dinner table and in the bedroom) (Castells et al., 2006). It is also important to note that the bulk of media consumption learning happens during leisure time for teenagers, who gain social skills via the usage of smartphones. Many mobile advertising efforts are expected to be aimed at teenagers in the future since they constitute a large share of early mobile service users and have developed a high level of mobile consumption expertise. Marketers realise that being always and everywhere connected via mobile phones can be seen as an excellent opportunity to advertise, build and develop customer relationships, and receive immediate feedback from those customers, which has led to an increase in mobile advertising budgets, particularly among younger demographics. It is anticipated that \$20.6 billion will be spent worldwide on mobile advertising in 2015 because of advertisers' desire. Europe had a 358 per cent increase in mobile advertising spending in 2011 alone, while Spain saw a 722 per cent increase. Marketers must understand the drivers and obstacles to mobile advertising acceptance because of the significance of mobile advertising. An essential aspect of mobile marketing research is how consumers feel about mobile advertising and whether or not they will embrace it. Anger and amusement have been recognized as the emotional predecessors of attitudes toward mobile

advertising. Studying mobile advertising-induced irritation has been done. However, there is a lack of investigation into fury as a direct antecedent of consumer attitude. The perception of advertising value has been linked to a positive attitude toward mobile advertising. Still, little research has examined the link between a positive attitude toward mobile advertising and discomfort. Customers like the ease with which mobile ads may be accessed. A customer's inbox is a convenient place to save promotional communications they don't want to lose track of until they're ready to act. In this respect, factors influencing mobile advertising adoption may be considered essential. Affective and cognitive predispositions to attitudes and behaviours toward mobile advertising have received less attention in prior studies than innovation-based drivers or utilitarian consumer-driven variables such as perceived control, trust, and sacrifice (Kumari, 2019).

Theoretical framework

The theories of “the magic bullet” and the “Uses and the gratification” are related to the research topic. As the topic of research regarding the like or dislike and the level of attraction of the youngsters towards the emerging trends in an advertisement, these theories will help us analyze the mass communication and the flow of movements. Both approaches are related to the case communication theory of social media and the consciousness of the user, which will help to understand the effect of emerging advertisements on the youngster. The theory of “uses and the gratification theory” introduces the four factors through which the audience sets their base to decide on their favourite platform. The factors are entertainment, culture and content. Similarly, in the magic bullet theory, the knowledge is communicated to the audience they did not possess first. The scope of emerging advertisement trends is to target the mass audience on different platforms and share the knowledge of their product in a manner they like. This means they target their culture, means of entertainment, and so.

Methodology

A researcher's philosophical viewpoint and the nature of the social science phenomena to be studied should be considered while choosing a research technique, according to Holden and Lynch. Goulding, on the other hand, believes that the researcher's interests, opinions, and convictions should guide the choice of technique. Choosing a study technique must also consider other important considerations, such as epistemological problems. Observed variables, such as the quantity of existing data or information, available time, and other resources, might influence a researcher's selection on which technique to adopt, in addition to philosophical foundations and personal opinions.

Research question

Research questions are "questions that a study is designed to address." Identifying a research question in quantitative and qualitative research methods is necessary. To conduct an investigation, you'll need to collect and analyze a wide range of data. To further our knowledge of an important issue, good research questions must be narrowly focused and specialized (Hernandez, 2020).

The research questions for this research are as follows:

- What is the impact of advertisements on the buying behavior of teenagers?
- How does the ad influence teenagers?
- What kind of advertisement attracts teenagers more?

Variable of study

The scope which one is trying to find is called a "variable" in the research context. Identifying that the phrases used to describe the variables imply the meanings of the variables themselves is the quickest and most straightforward way to understand the difference between two types of variables (de Assis Lago, 2019):

- independent variables
- dependent variable.

Independent variables

This constant is not affected by the other variables being assessed. It's a way of describing an experiment in which the researcher has complete control over the variables. It's most likely the explanation behind the incident. In this case, the independent variables are:

- Brand
- Advertising trends

Dependent variables

The parameter is dependent on other parameters being assessed. The manipulation of the independent variable or variables is expected to influence these variables. It's what we anticipated. In this case, the dependent variables are as follows:

- Teenagers' choice
- Buying behaviour

Research design

It serves as a guide for data collection, measurement, and interpretation. When conducting a research project, the general method used to integrate the many components of the study to ensure that the research issue is appropriately handled is known as research design. A study design aims to provide that the data acquired allows one to answer the research problem as logically and clearly as possible. Identifying the evidence needed to test a theory, assessing a programme, or accurately characterize and evaluate the relevance of an observable phenomenon is expected in the social sciences. As a result, researchers often make the mistake of starting their investigations much too early before assessing what information is required to address the study's issue. These design issues must be addressed at the beginning of every research project. Otherwise, the study's findings would be inadequate and incoherent. This will impact the study's overall validity (Gates, 2022).

Quantitative research

Quantitative research methods are typically adopted because they are scientific methods and provide immediate results. Other reason for selecting this approach is that it is more suitable, can test hypothesis and always aimed at clarifying features, count them and build statistical model to explain what is observed during research .in this study, quantitative methods of structured survey will be used.

Universe

The universe of this research is Pakistan's advertisement platforms, primarily social media platforms such as Facebook, tic tokk, Instagram and such. The brand launches its advertisement on these platforms, targeting the required audience.

Survey

As a method of data collection, surveys include asking a set number of people questions to elicit information and insights on a wide range of topics. It is possible to perform them in some methods, depending on the methodology utilized, the study's purpose, and the research question.

Population

The target audiences are youngster's and other age groups, people. This way, we will be able to identify the buying behavior of youngsters and differentiate it from the buying behaviours of the different age groups. In this research work the population is the public of Pakistan (Lahore). There were 500 surveys held to support this research, and this was the mix of age, gender, and the taste of shopping participants.

Sampling

The sampling consisted of different types of participants. They belong to other age groups, which define the alien in the mindset and thinking strategy. They were of both genders to avoid biases based on a single gender. Most importantly, they were of different educational and cultural backgrounds. This shows the variation in the taste and the priority and the influence of emerging trends of advertisement over them and their buying behaviours.

Operationalization of terms

The terms used in this research are as follows (de Assis Lago, 2019):

- Brands
- Audience/ social media
- Brands
- Buying behaviours

Brands

To differentiate your firm, you need a brand. How your customers see and engage with your business is what matters most. Customer service, staff attire, business cards, marketing materials, and advertising contribute to a good brand. It would help if you did comprehensive market research to build a strong brand. To ensure that customers remember your company's products and services, you must have a strong brand identity. Brand loyalty is shared among customers. It's essential to start thinking about branding as soon as you decide to start a business since it increases your chances of being successful (Beck, 2019).

Audience

The audience of this research is teenagers. The term "teenager" refers to someone 13 to 19 years old. Due to their age ending in "teen," they are called "adolescents." Adulthood and adolescence are sometimes used interchangeably. According to most neurologists, the human brain is still developing into its adult form until about the age of twenty-five or even later. When you turn 13, you're officially a teen until you become 20. 18 and 19-year-olds may be considered adults in certain jurisdictions, depending on where they live (Cai, 2022).

Social media

Communication, community feedback, involvement in creating information, and cooperation are all hallmarks of social media. People use social media to stay in touch with their friends, family, and the people in the communities they belong to. Businesses use social networking sites to sell and advertise their products and monitor customers' feedback and concerns. User- comment areas are common on business-to-consumer websites. The monitoring, measurement, and analysis of public attention to brands and products on social media are all made possible by various technologies. The use of social media has grown tremendously during the last few years. Access to these platforms is made easier thanks to mobile applications. Popular social networks include Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and more (Tan, 2019).

Buying behaviours

Before making a purchase, shoppers (both online and off) engage in certain behaviours known as "Consumer Buying Behavior." Search engines, social media interaction, and a variety of other activities may be used in this process. Understanding this process is helpful to businesses because it enables them to better focus their marketing initiatives on those that have worked in the past.

Findings and results

The results generated by this research in the path to achieving the goal. In these results, some of the questions were asked to the general public. Here, we have surveyed the 500 public. the question that was asked and their response is as follows:

Brand

In the survey, the public was asked whether they were brand conscious in the help the researchers identify the mindset and the taste of the public participating survey with us. This helps to identify and allows us to see how the taste of the general and their trend on social media are in sync with one another. This was the question in the people had to share their opinion based on agree or disagreement. The survey results show that about 16.23% of the public strongly disagreed with being brand conscious and differ. While 20.64% strongly agreed and 24.25% agreed they are brand conscious. At the same time, the remaining 20.64% of the public is neutral about whether they are brand conscious or not

Sophisticated customer

In the survey, the public was asked whether they were sophisticated customers in the study to help the researchers identify the type of customer available and targeted by over- analysis in the public participating in the survey with us. This helps with the shopping style of the participants and their choice and attitude towards shopping and brands, and hence the advertising. According to the survey, about 19.44% strongly disagree, and 19.44% disagree that they are more sophisticated shoppers than their ancestors. Whereas 24.45 % agree and 23.05 strongly agree that they are more sophisticated shoppers than their ancestors. At the same time, 13.43% are neutral about it. The graphical representation of these numbers is as follows:

Online platforms

In the survey, the general public was asked about their preference for the platforms and their trust level to help the researchers identify the general public's trust in the online shopping platforms by participating in the survey with us. This helps to identify the general public's level of trust in online shopping brands' media. According to the study, about 14.83% strongly disagree, and 20.44% disagree that social platform has gained.

Advertisement influence

In the survey, the general public was asked whether the advertisement easily influenced them in the study to help the researchers identify the effect of the emerging advertising trends on the general public participating in the survey with us. This helps to determine the impact of the advertisement of brands or product's advertisement on the general public and their view. According to the survey data, about 41.88 % admit that advertising influences their buying behaviour, whereas 29.86% deny that. However, 28.26%are confused regarding the influence of advertisements on their buying behaviour. The graphical representation of these numbers is as follows:

Celebs in advertisement

In the survey, the general public was asked whether the celebs in the advertisement affect their decision-making power or not in the study to help the researchers identify the effect of celebrities in ads over the general public that is participating in the survey with us. This helps to identify the role of the celebs in the emerging trends of the advertisement and so. According to the survey data, 44.09% admit that the celebrities in the ad influence them, and they tend to shop more for such products. Whereas 28.08% disagree with this, they deny the influence of celebs over buying behaviour. At the same time, the remaining 27.05% are neutral about this. The graphical representation of these numbers is as follows:

Attractive packaging

In the survey, the general public was asked about their opinions about the effect of making on their buying behaviour of the product in the study to help the researchers identify the impact of attractive packaging of the product by brands over the general public that is participating in the survey with us. This helps to determine the influence of the beautiful package of the product over the buying behaviour of the general public. According to the survey data, about 13.83% strongly disagree, and 17.64% disagree with the thought of their buying behaviours being influenced by attractive packaging. In comparison, 20.84 agree, and 39.66% strongly agree that the beautiful packaging of the product affects their buying. However, 17.84% are neutral about this. The visual representation of these figures is as follows:

Funny and colourful

In the survey, the general public was asked about the effect of the funny and colourful content of the advertisement on their buying behavior to help the researchers identify the development of the content of advertisements on the buying behaviours of the general public participating in the survey with us. This helps to identify and analyze the impact of the funny and colourful content of the advertisement on emerging trends in the buying behaviours of the participant. According to the survey data, about 16.83% strongly disagreed, and 16.83% disagreed with the advertisement's content. Whereas 28.26% agreed, and 22.24 strongly agreed that the content does influence them. At the same time, 15.63% of the public is neutral about this. The visual representation of these figures is as follows:

Boost social image

In the survey, the general public was asked about their opinion of the participants to determine their buying behaviours linked to their social image survey to help the researchers identify the link between the

Do you generally look for an easy solution to boost your social image by falling prey to these ads?

buying behaviour and the social image of the general public participating in the study with us. This helps to identify the connection between the participant's social image and the participant's buying behaviours. According to the survey data, about 22.04% strongly disagree, and 13063% disagree that they participate in buying behaviour or activities to boost their social image, whereas 27.25% agree and 17.23% strongly agree to improve their colonial appearance. The remaining neutral at this point. The visual representation of this data is as follows:

Ego

In the survey, the general public was asked about the link between the ego and their buying behaviour to help the researchers identify and analyze the general public participating in the survey with us. This helps to understand the link between the buying behaviour of the participants influenced by their ego. According to the survey data, about 38.08% think that advertisements influence their ego, while 29.86% disagree with the remaining 32.06% of the public is neutral about it. The graphical representation of the data is as follows:

Luxury

In the survey, the general public was asked about the link between luxury desire and their buying behaviour to help the research identity analysis of the association by the general public participating in the survey with us. This helps to understand the connection between the buying behaviour of the participants influenced by their luxurious desires. According to the survey data, about 16.23% strongly disagree, and 16.23% disagree that their buying behaviour and passion for luxury are linked. In comparison, 20.84% agree, and 28.06% strongly agree about the existence of a link. The remaining 18.44% are neutral about it. The graphical representation of the data is as follows:

Problem solvers

In the survey, the general public was asked whether this advertisement solves the problem of their influences in the study to help the researcher identify the role of the advertisement as a problem solver by the general public participating in the survey with us. This helps us to understand the role of emerging trends of advertisement as the problem solver for the participants. According to the survey data, about 39.08% think the emerging advertising trend is a problem solver, while 31.26% disagree with this. The remaining 29.66% are neutral about this. The graphical representation of these figures is following:

Control

In the survey, the general public was asked about the link between the control over their buying behaviour to help the researchers identify and analyse the connection between the management and their will over buying of the general public participating in the study with us. This helps to determine the nature of control and the participant's willpower over the advertisement's emerging trend over the participant. According to the survey data, about 16.03% strongly disagree, and 14.83 % disagree that the emerging advertising trend controls them, whereas 21.84% agree and 27.25% strongly agree that this is handling them. At the same time, the remaining 20.04% are neutral about this. The graphical representation of the figures is as follows:

Power

In the survey, the general public was asked of their whether the emerging trend had power over their thinking strategy or not in the study to help the researchers identify and analyse the link between the thinking strategy and the emerging trends the general public that is participating in in the survey with us. This helps to understand the connection between the buying behaviours and the thinking strategy of the participants. According to the survey data, 42.28% of the general public thinks that the emerging advertisement trend has power over their thinking strategy, while 27.05 does not. The remaining 30.66% are neutral about this. The graphical representation of the figures stated are as follows:

Positive message

In the survey, the general public was asked whether the emerging trends of advertisement communicate any positive message to them in the study to help the researchers identify and analyse the communication of the ad to the general public participating in the study with us. This helps to send understand whether the emerging trends are communicating a positive message to the participants or not. According to the survey

data, 43.29% of the general public thinks that the emerging advertisement trend conveys positive messages, while 24.25% do not. The remaining 32.26% are neutral about this. The graphical representation of the figures stated are as follows:

RQ1 What is the impact of advertisement on the buying behaviour of the youth?

The advertisement is to educate the targeted audience about their product and the services so that the target audience understands the best. By doing so, the brands aim to have control and power over the buying behaviours of the youth to drive them to the path and the direction they wish. The advertisement appears to the targeted audience as the problem solver to their concerns and solution to maintain their ego and social image.

RQ2 How do advertisements influence youth?

Youth have crazed social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat and such. The emerging trend of advertising uses these platforms to target their audience effectively. Additionally, in the advertisement, the young people are convinced that the product is a problem solver and has the capability of problem-solving and ego satisfaction

RQ3 What kind of advertisement attracts the youth more?

The emerging advertisement trend uses funny and colourful content to attract thru targeted audience and maintain their decision power over their buying behaviour. The ad is made to bind the target audience and unconsciously make them feel they need that product for survival and to maintain their social image and ego.

Discussion and Conclusion

In conclusion, the emerging trend of advertisement is to target the audience to introduce their brand to have control and power over their buying behaviours. This means that now, the brands are aiming for such a scheme to control and drive the behaviours of their audience. In the end, the researcher was in the position to answer the research question which was being asked in the methodology section.

There were many factors from which the conclusion can be drawn. Some of them are as follows:

- The effect of the emerging trend of an advertisement on the youth depends upon the choice and the taste of the targeted audience. The ratio of people who like and dislike the concept of an emerging trend is almost balanced, and one can say it's a 50 – 50 ratio
- One can say that emerging trends' effect on youth depends on their personality. For some, the emerging trend promoted itself among them by using their ego, social image and brand-conscious nature, while others disagree with it. Similarly, these ratios are also almost equal.
- Apart from this, there was a finding that how the ego and mindset of the youngster effect buying behaviors and the medium they prefer for their shopping purpose. There are some youngsters who

think that they are more sophisticated than their ancestor in the shopping matter while others are on some different page.

- The survey shows that there is a divergence of thinking process according to youngsters' own previous experience, background and the family and friends circle they have and wants. The effect of emerging trends is more on the youngsters who are brand concisions, shopping fam and such. Where there is little or no effect of the trends on the remaining.

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